

FAMILY AS A SILENT DECISION-MAKER IN PRIVATE UNIVERSITY ENROLLMENT: EVIDENCE FROM TASHKENT

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Abstract

In many higher education systems, university enrollment choices are seen to be as individual choices guided by academic interests, preferences the trends in the market. (Hemsley-Brown & Oplatka, 2015; Kotler & Fox, 1995). In Uzbekistan, students, that apply to private universities do not make the decision themselves alone. This conference paper is based on the results driven from doctoral PhD dissertation on socio-cultural determinants with regards to private university choices in Tashkent, Uzbekistan and examines the way enrollment decisions are formed and shaped after going through filters of family discussions, shared value judgments, and social expectations the exist in Tashkent. Based on a mixed-methods approach study of 275 students that are enrolled in private universities of the capital Tashkent, the paper combined google survey with qualitative student accounts in order to demonstrate how Uzbek families act as the early gatekeepers of the admission process for the students, it is a pattern that is widely observed in collectivist and post-Soviet societies (Hofstede, 2011; Marginson, 2016). The findings of the study indicated that perceived value acts as a unified judgment which combines degree recognition, affordability, teaching quality, reputation, and future employment prospects of the students upon graduation private universities, rather than as a separate attribute (Soutar & Turner, 2002; Nguyen & LeBlanc, 2001). Among these variables and determinants, degree recognition emerges as the most decisive and pivotal concern for families of the students, it reflected its role in reducing uncertainty and showing institutional trust in private higher education institutions (Altbach et al., 2019). Marketing communication as a key player increases visibility but it does not determine the final enrollment decisions, in fact the decisions are settled after going through filters of discussion and family approval and social validation, this is consistent with earlier research on higher education choice in collectivist societies (Maringe, 2006; Wilkins & Huisman, 2015). This paper argues that if we want to understand private university enrollment in Uzbekistan, it requires us to shift our attention from individual choice models toward decision's that are family oriented.

Keywords: private universities, enrollment decisions, family influence, perceived value, Uzbekistan, higher education marketing

1. Introduction

Private higher education sector of Uzbekistan has expanded very rapidly over the past decade, and we have been witnessing the establishments of new institutions appearing in Tashkent as we move on where these institutions and offer programs across various fields such as business, economics, information

technology, and international studies (Altbach et al., 2019; OECD, 2020). This expansion has diversified the number and type of choices for students residing in Tashkent and those coming to the capital city from other provinces, at the same time it has also introduced some level of uncertainty for families. There are questions and doubts regarding degree recognition, high tuition fees, and long-term outcomes which are frequently raised by families when private universities are at the center of discussions at home, particularly in systems where private higher education is still consolidating its public legitimacy and Uzbekistan is not an exception (Marginson, 2016).

Most of the literature from international journals and sources on university choice emphasizes individual preferences of the students, employability, and marketing exposure to a high magnitude. However, these mentioned approaches in the international publications and literature often assume that students evaluate options independently and respond directly to promotional messages given by private institutions (Hemsley-Brown & Oplatka, 2015; Maringe, 2006). In collectivist and post-Soviet countries such as Uzbekistan, this assumption and prejudice does not fully reflect and resonate with everyday decision-making practices and process. Since students commonly involve their parents and relatives from the earliest stages of the admission process unlike many other individualist societies, because education is often treated as a shared family investment here rather than an individual decision to be made by the students (Hofstede, 2011; Wilkins & Huisman, 2015).

This paper thoroughly and comprehensively explores how and in what ways enrollment decisions in private universities in Tashkent are shaped through students and their family involvement as well as the shared evaluations of value. It furthermore focuses on what students report about conversations at home, the concerns raised by parents during the discussions, and the role marketing communication plays within these discussions in a quest to recruit students.

2. Literature Background

Previous studies on student's enrollment decisions have been able to identify a range of factors that influence students' university choices, including academic quality, reputation of the institutions, affordability and reasonable tuition fees, and expected career outcomes upon graduation (Soutar & Turner, 2002; Maringe, 2006). Many of those studies have also recognized the role of parental influence, particularly in collectivist societies higher education of the young generation is seen and considered as pride and an family investment rather than a purely independent decision that students themselves have to make (Hofstede, 2011; Chen et al., 2021). In such settings and contexts, the enrollment decisions are often discussed within households and are shaped based on shared expectations about security, status, and long-term returns.

Research that focuses on post-Soviet contexts further emphasize the importance of risk avoidance and social stability in higher education choice because families mostly tend to prioritize and recommend institutions that

appear legitimate, socially accepted, and formally recognized and this is a critical issue that can not be ignored by the parents (Marginson, 2016). Degree recognition and institutional trust often become central reference points during admission discussions for families in Tashkent, especially when private universities are considered, since there are serious concerns about the future of the family investments if a particular private institution is shut down or goes bankrupt (Altbach et al., 2019). While marketing-oriented studies highlight the remarkable and high level of the use of digital promotion and branding in higher education sphere, evidence from collectivist environments suggests that these channels rarely operate independently and instead, marketing messages are filtered through family discussions and community validation before influencing enrollment decisions for private universities (Wilkins & Huisman, 2015).

Much of the existing literature on university choice and student enrollment has been developed in Western contexts where societies are more individualistically oriented and these studies typically portray students as independent decision-makers who respond directly to academic rankings, employability indicators, and institutional branding and upon weighting the variables make decisions on their own (Hemsley-Brown & Oplatka, 2015). Marketing communication and promotion specifically via digital tools is often presented as a primary driver of enrollment intentions, with limited attention given to family involvement or collective evaluation processes which dominates in post-soviet countries.

In contrast, some rare studies from Asia, the Middle East, and post-Soviet regions highlights few aspects that shows correlation and proves the families to be in the center of the decision-making process for private institutions. In these contexts, families and parents actively evaluate private universities by weighting degree recognition, social acceptance, affordability of the tuitions, and future employment perspectives (Maringe, 2006; Nguyen & LeBlanc, 2001). Promotional appeal and any sort of marketing campaigns alone falls short and insufficient to secure enrollment if these shared concerns of the guardians are not addressed through the campaigns.

Despite these insights derived from research, relatively no study particularly in Asia has integrated all the following determinates such as family influence, perceived value, and marketing communication into one single empirical analysis focused on private universities in Uzbekistan aimed at developing a student-centric model. The existing literature frequently examines the mentioned factors in isolation or concentrates on public higher education institutions. As a result, there remains limited empirical understanding of how enrollment decisions in private universities are formed within family and social settings in Tashkent. This gap provides the basis for the present study, which draws on students' lived enrollment experiences to examine these influences together.

3. Methodology

The study used a mixed methods design approach to capture both measurable patterns and socially embedded decision practices in Tashkent with regards to university enrollment choices, an approach commonly applied when numerical trends and lived experiences need to be interpreted together (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). Quantitative data for the research were collected through a structured google survey completed by 275 students enrolled in private universities in Tashkent and students in the last year of their schooling, about to make the university choice. The survey measured factors that were always looked at in isolation such as family influence, perceived value (quality, degree recognition, affordability, reputation, and career prospects), exposure to marketing communication, and demographic characteristics including gender and age to draw a complete picture of how decision are shaped in the context of Tashkent.

Qualitative data were gathered and collected through open-ended survey questions, where students described how enrollment decisions were influenced at home and how concerns were raised and resolved. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, reliability testing, correlation analysis, and regression modeling, which are the most widely utilized techniques in research concerning higher education sector and the relationships among decision factors (Field, 2018). Qualitative responses derived from the surveys were reviewed thematically to identify recurring patterns and explanations, it was followed by established qualitative analysis procedures and processes (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

The focus on currently enrolled students made it possible to examine completed enrollment decisions about university enrollment choice rather than hypothetical intentions which enabled this research to reduce response bias (Maringe, 2006). Although parents and family members were not surveyed directly by this survey but parental and socio cultural influences were clearly reflected in students' descriptions of household discussions and university choice approval processes. The mixed-methods approach allowed numerical results to be interpreted alongside these everyday accounts and it also ensured that statistical patterns only reflect the social context in which enrollment decisions are being made

4. Findings

4.1 Family Influence as an Early Filter

Students consistently reported that families became involved before their applications were submitted to their preferred university options. Parents and relatives raised questions about diploma recognition primarily and then tuition affordability, and institutional reputation. Universities which were perceived as uncertain or unfamiliar were mostly excluded early, regardless of the coverage and excellence of their marketing visibility across platforms. This pattern indicated that enrollment decisions are socially filtered at an early stage by family approval and shapes the list of which institutions are considered acceptable

before students engage more deeply with institutional information desks, it is a finding consistent with earlier studies on family gatekeeping in higher education choice (Maringe, 2006; Wilkins & Huisman, 2015).

4.2 Perceived Value as a Unified Judgment

Survey results of this research showed that perceived value did not operate as separate attributes in isolation and rather students and their families discussed issues such as teaching quality, degree recognition, cost, reputation, and employment prospects upon graduation together as part of a single evaluation process. It is a pattern that is consistent with earlier research on holistic value assessment in higher education choice (Soutar & Turner, 2002; Nguyen & LeBlanc, 2001). Regression analysis in the research indicated that degree recognition was the strongest predictor of overall perceived value, it highlighted its role as a signal of trust and without trust its obvious that no sale can be made. This suggests that families highly rely and emphasize on the issue of degree recognition in order to reduce uncertainty and evaluate private universities as a whole rather than comparing individual elements and features in isolation, particularly in contexts where institutional legitimacy is closely scrutinized (Altbach et al., 2019).

4.3 Gender Differences in Evaluation

Gender-related differences appeared in both quantitative and qualitative data in the research on influencing determinants. It is found that families tended to apply stricter checks related to the safety, social acceptance, and approval when the applicant was female member of their family. While for male student members of the family, discussions more frequently emphasized and revolved around employment outcomes and public recognition of the institution in Uzbekistan and abroad. These patterns show that enrollment decisions are negotiated highly within gender-specific expectations that influence the way families assess risk and future outcomes. It is a finding that goes consistently with earlier research on gendered family involvement in higher education choice (Maringe, 2006; Wilkins & Huisman, 2015; Chen et al., 2021).

4.4 The Role of Marketing Communication

Marketing communication mainly helped families and students only become aware of the available private university options and the their facilities. Digital promotion, campus visits, and word-of-mouth introduced universities into conversations but rarely played the pivotal role as decisive element. Final enrollment choices were typically made only after family discussion and confirmation from trusted social sources were obtained. This indicated that marketing messages function as entry points into the decision process signaling the availability and facilities as well as informative info regarding tuition, validity of expert international lectures, easy commuting routes and so on rather than as decisive drivers of enrollment, it is a significant pattern observed in studies of higher education marketing in collectivist and family-influenced contexts (Maringe, 2006; Hemsley-Brown & Oplatka, 2015; Wilkins & Huisman, 2015).

5. Discussion

The findings of this research indicate that enrollment in private universities in Tashkent is only best understood when a socially embedded process is considered rather than an individual decision that is driven by personal preference alone. Students rarely interpret information independently in Tashkent context. Instead, their families guide how information must be discussed, questioned, and accepted. Parents and relatives in fact act as silent decision-makers by filtering options early, raising concerns about issues such as degree recognition, affordability, and long-term security, it shapes which universities shall remain acceptable. Similar patterns of family-mediated decision-making also have been observed in collectivist and post-Soviet higher education contexts (Hofstede, 2011; Marginson, 2016). The element of Perceived value therefore functions as a shared family judgment lens, where different attributes and influencing elements are evaluated all together. In the contest of Uzbekistan, degree recognition plays a central role in this process by reducing uncertainty and signaling legitimacy in systems where private higher education is still consolidating its status (Altbach et al., 2019).

These patterns help us to explain why marketing communication operates differently from what is often assumed in individual-choice models. Promotional activities and campaigns only increased awareness and introduce universities into family conversations, but they do not determine the final enrollment outcomes and decisions. Visibility alone is insufficient and falls short if family concerns about trust and legitimacy remain unresolved. Studies of higher education marketing in non-Western societies show that branding and digital promotion doesn't directly lead into enrollment decisions without the presence of social validation oriented around families (Hemsley-Brown & Oplatka, 2015; Wilkins & Huisman, 2015). In contexts such as Tashkent, where decisions are firstly negotiated collectively in the family settings, to create effective enrollment strategies private institution need to align their marketing communication strategies with family-based evaluations of value and risks.

6. Conclusion

This conference paper demonstrates that enrollment decisions for private universities in Tashkent emerge and shapes through family-led discussions first rather than through individual choice alone like decisions made in non-collectivist societies. Uzbek Students rarely decide in isolation and instead, their parents and relatives also take part in the process from the very early stages, raising questions, and they shape which institutions are to be viewed as acceptable, it is a pattern which is widely noted in collectivist and family-oriented higher education contexts (Hofstede, 2011; Marginson, 2016). Families evaluate and envision perceived value as a unified judgment package that includes not only one or two isolated factors but a group of determinants such as degree recognition, affordability, teaching quality, reputation, and future employment prospects. Among these mentioned elements, degree recognition is on the top and

plays a particularly important role by reducing uncertainty for families and even student, in fact it signals institutional trust in private higher education (Altbach et al., 2019).

The findings of this research also clarify the role of marketing communication in the decision-making process for private institutions in Tashkent. Primarily promotional activities help students and families become more aware of available university options and their product offerings, but they do not determine final enrollment outcomes. Decisions are usually finalized after being filtered within family discussions and also social confirmation rather than in response to private university advertising campaigns alone, consistent with earlier research on the limits of marketing-driven enrollment in non-Western contexts (Hemsley-Brown & Oplatka, 2015; Wilkins & Huisman, 2015). In conclusion the result of this study strongly emphasizes that admission strategies by universities in the local context of Tashkent must account for the collective nature of decision-making process in the capital city. Approaches and strategies that put the family concerns in the center and address them directly by reflecting how enrollment decisions are discussed in practice are more likely to align with the realities of private higher education in Tashkent.

References

- Altbach, P. G., Reisberg, L., & Rumbley, L. E. (2019). Trends in global higher education: Tracking an academic revolution (2nd ed.). Brill.
- Hemsley-Brown, J., & Oplatka, I. (2015). Higher education consumer choice. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Hofstede, G. (2011). Dimensionalizing cultures: The Hofstede model in context. *Online Readings in Psychology and Culture*, 2(1), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.9707/2307-0919.1014>
- Kotler, P., & Fox, K. F. A. (1995). Strategic marketing for educational institutions (2nd ed.). Prentice Hall.
- Maringe, F. (2006). University and course choice: Implications for positioning, recruitment and marketing. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 20(6), 466–479. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513540610683711>
- Marginson, S. (2016). The worldwide trend to high participation higher education: Dynamics of social stratification in inclusive systems. *Higher Education*, 72(4), 413–434. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-016-0016-x>
- Nguyen, N., & LeBlanc, G. (2001). Image and reputation of higher education institutions in students' retention decisions. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 15(6), 303–311. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513540110401453>

- Soutar, G. N., & Turner, J. P. (2002). Students' preferences for university: A conjoint analysis. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 16(1), 40–45. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513540210415523>
- Wilkins, S., & Huisman, J. (2015). Factors affecting university choice in the United Arab Emirates. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 37(3), 285–300. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2015.1034429>
- Altbach, P. G., Reisberg, L., & Rumbley, L. E. (2019). *Trends in global higher education: Tracking an academic revolution* (2nd ed.). Brill.
- Hemsley-Brown, J., & Oplatka, I. (2015). *Higher education consumer choice*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Hofstede, G. (2011). Dimensionalizing cultures: The Hofstede model in context. *Online Readings in Psychology and Culture*, 2(1), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.9707/2307-0919.1014>
- Maringe, F. (2006). University and course choice: Implications for positioning, recruitment and marketing. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 20(6), 466–479. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513540610683711>
- Marginson, S. (2016). The worldwide trend to high participation higher education: Dynamics of social stratification in inclusive systems. *Higher Education*, 72(4), 413–434. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-016-0016-x>
- OECD. (2020). *Education in Central Asia: Reforms and challenges*. OECD Publishing.
- Wilkins, S., & Huisman, J. (2015). Factors affecting university choice in the United Arab Emirates. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 37(3), 285–300. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2015.1034429>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2018). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research* (3rd ed.). Sage.
- Field, A. (2018). *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics* (5th ed.). Sage.
- Maringe, F. (2006). University and course choice: Implications for positioning, recruitment and marketing. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 20(6), 466–479. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513540610683711>
- Altbach, P. G., Reisberg, L., & Rumbley, L. E. (2019). *Trends in global higher education: Tracking an academic revolution* (2nd ed.). Brill.

Nguyen, N., & LeBlanc, G. (2001). Image and reputation of higher education institutions in students' retention decisions. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 15(6), 303–311. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513540110401453>

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